

N-NO & NN-O bond cleavage dynamics in two- and three-body Coulomb explosion of the N_2O^{2+} dication.

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Triatomic Coulomb explosion dynamics are initiated by single-photon double ionization of N_2O with an ultrafast EUV pulse and are probed by delayed near-IR pulses. The triatomic benchmark system exhibits competing two- and three-body dissociation dynamics that are reflected in the time resolved branching ratios and in the co-linear three-body momentum correlation spectra. Both the N-NO and the NN-O bond dissociation channels result in vibrationally excited molecular products. Channel resolved kinetic energy release (KER) spectra exhibit shifts emerging at long probe delays of hundreds of femtoseconds. The asymptotic shifts, towards lower KER indicate that the long-range Coulomb repulsion is effectively screened at bond-distances above $\sim 16 \text{ \AA}$, at which the Rydberg electron is localized on one of the dissociating fragments. Thus, revealing up to a 0.9 eV gap that develops between the molecular Rydberg ion state and its core at long bond distance.

Introduction

Description of bond breaking dynamics of excited polyatomic systems is one of the great challenges of experimental and theoretical quantum chemistry. In particular, understanding the dissociation dynamics of multiply-ionized systems is essential to developing various applications implementing highly ionizing radiation. For example applications such as Coulomb explosion imaging (CEI),¹⁻⁸ single-shot crystallography,⁹⁻¹¹ as well as time resolved photoelectron spectroscopy¹²⁻¹⁴ and microscopy.^{15,16} These types of applications utilize ionizing radiation of intense fs-laser pulses, produced by chirped pulse amplification,¹⁷ attosecond EUV pulses produced by high harmonic generation (HHG),^{18,19} as well as ultrafast XUV and X-ray pulses produced in free electron laser facilities.^{11,20} In addition to man-made laboratory conditions, multiply-ionized systems dynamics occur naturally in different planetary and inter-stellar environments due to the ionizing cosmic ray radiation.^{21,22}

Unravelling competing bond cleavage mechanisms of two- and three-body dissociation processes in simple triatomic

understanding dynamics of more complex multiply-ionized polyatomic systems. Accordingly, the Coulomb explosion (CE) of N_2O^{2+} has attracted significant experimental and theoretic attention.²³⁻³² Early experiments have demonstrated the favourable cleavage of the N-NO versus the NN-O bond, observed following double ionization of the linear N_2O molecule by electron impact,^{23,24} double charge transfer with fast protons or highly charged ions,^{25,26} as well as photoionization.²⁶⁻²⁸

Figure 1 shows the potential landscape of the doubly ionized N_2O^{2+} states. The energies were calculated by Taylor *et al* on the MRCI level as a function of elongating either the N-NO or the NN-O bond-distance, starting from the linear Frank-Condon (FC) geometry of the parent neutral molecule.²⁹ The $X^3\Sigma_g^-$ ground state can lead to the dissociation of the N-NO bond or the NN-O bond.²⁸⁻³⁰ While the barrier towards the N-NO bond cleavage is clearly lower than the FC potential, NN-O cleavage is predicted to proceed above low lying shallow barriers on the multi-dimensional ground-state surface.^{29,30} In contrast,³¹ the excited triplet state exhibits significant barriers towards both product channels and can be expected to be meta-stable, as supported by the observation of intact N_2O^{2+} dications by Eland

Figure 1: Full lines show the N_2O^{2+} potential landscape on the MRCI level as a function of N-NO or NN-O bond extensions from the FC geometry, reproduced from the lower lying potentials calculated by Taylor *et al*.²⁹ The triplet states are shown by the magenta lines, while black lines represent the singlet states. Dashed line represents schematically a Rydberg ion state with a $X^3\Sigma_g^-$ dication core. The shaded green region illustrates the expected gap between the Rydberg ion state and its dication core due to screening of the long range Coulomb repulsion. Blue and green arrows indicate possible one and two-photon transitions at the transient FC geometry that lead to the observed transient NN-O : N-NO enhancement. Black arrow indicates possible photoexcitation of the N_2^+ product, assigned to the NN-O : N-NO suppression at long times. Red arrows indicate Rydberg state ionization transitions, responsible for the observed KER shifts at long time delays.

benchmark systems such as N_2O is an important step towards and co-workers.²⁹ The low lying $1^1\Delta$ and $1^1\Sigma^+$ states exhibit high

barriers for breaking the NN-O bond and are predicted to contribute only to N-NO cleavage.³⁰ In contrast, the higher 1Π state is expected to preferentially dissociate the NN-O bond.²⁹ Three-body dissociation into the $N^+ + N + O^+$ was reported by Price *et al*, using He(II) radiation.²⁶ Furthermore, at higher excitation energies, tri-cation Coulomb explosions into $N^+ + N^+ + O^+$ were studied using intense near-IR fs-laser pulses,³¹ as well as collisions with highly charged Ar^{8+} and Xe^{15+} .²⁵

Several experimental studies using ultrafast pulses explored the possibility to control the competing N-NO and NN-O bond breaking channels by manipulating the peak intensity^{31,32} or carrier envelope phase³³ of intense fs-laser pulses in the near-IR. Furthermore, Zhou *et al* explored strong field control of the ultrafast bond-breaking dynamics by an intense near-IR pulse, time delayed with respect to its 27th harmonic pump pulse, produced by HHG.³⁴ The 27th harmonic at $\sim 43\text{eV}$ photon energy excites N_2O near and below the double ionization threshold, resulting in strong enhancements of both two-body breakup channels due to strong-field ionization of high lying cation states excited below the double ionization threshold.³⁴ While Zhou *et al* considered non-Rydberg like states, the dashed line in figure 1 shows schematically the expected potential of a Rydberg ion state with a $X^3\Sigma_g^-$ dication core. Similar to neutral Rydberg states, at short bond-distances a Rydberg ion state mimics the potential of their dication core. However, it is important to note that at long distances, at which the Rydberg electron is confined only to one of the fragments, the long-range Coulomb repulsion can be effectively screened by the excess electron. Weakly bound neutral product of such dissociation can be ionized by the field of the nearby ion, resulting in the pair of cations. Nevertheless, sufficiently bound states can produce stable neutral fragments with high kinetic energy release (KER). Such high KER neutrals were previously reported and assigned to Rydberg ion states in intense laser interaction with neutral and anionic system.^{35–38}

Here, we explore the N_2O^{2+} dissociation dynamics, initiated by single photon double ionization using a broad bandwidth EUV pump pulse with photon energies up to 100eV, high above the double ionization threshold of $\sim 36\text{eV}$.^{29,30} The ultrafast breakup dynamics are probed by a time delayed near-IR pulse. Time resolved branching ratios, KER and three-body momentum correlations spectra are presented and discussed in terms of the ultrafast dynamics of competing N-NO and NN-O bond cleavage mechanisms. Furthermore, time resolved KER spectra reveal the potential gap between the Rydberg ion states and their molecular dication core, emerging due to screening of the long range Coulomb repulsion at long bond distances.

Results and discussion

Photoionization of N_2O by a single EUV photon with energies up to $\sim 100\text{eV}$, high above the double ionization threshold, is dominated by ionization of a single electron producing predominantly the intact N_2O^+ and the dissociative ionization NO^+ products. Nevertheless, over 4% of the total ion signal are

attributed to CE due to single-photon double-ionization. Using HHG in Neon and within the experimental signal to noise limits, we did not observe any significant yields of metastable N_2O^{2+} or yields of triple ionization channels. Two-body breakup dominates over three-body dissociation of the dication with a $\sim 33:5$ branching ratio in agreement with previous photoionization experiments.²⁶ Similarly, the two-body breakup channels resulting from NN-O and N-NO bond cleavage are

Figure 2: circles show the total CE yield as a function of near-IR probe delay (t_{nIR}) with respect to the EUV pump, where the colour of the fitted curve encodes the enhancement (ENH) of the 2:3 body breakup ratio. Square markers show the two-body CE yield, where the colour of the fitted curve encodes the NN-O : N-NO cleavage ratio ENH. For comparison the transient enhancement of single ionization N_2O^+ yield is shown by the * markers.

observed with a respective 5:13 branching ratio, also in agreement with previous photoionization studies.²⁸

Figure 2 presents the time resolved effect of a near-IR probe pulse on the competing product channels. The total yield of CE products as well as the partial yield of the two-body breakup channels are shown by the circle and square markers respectively. For comparison, the single ionization N_2O^+ signal, marked by asterisks, shows the ultrafast pump-probe cross-correlation time, fitted with a Gaussian instrumental response with a $\sigma \sim 35\text{fs}$ standard deviation. The CE yields are fitted with a combination of a Gaussian transient with a $\sigma \sim 85\text{fs}$ and a long-lived component that rises with the 35fs cross-correlation time. The fitted curves colours encode the time dependent enhancements of the NN-O : N-NO bond cleavage ratio in two body breakup and the three : two-body breakup ratio in the total CE yield. At negative times, at which the near-IR pulse arrives before the EUV excitation, the yields agree with those of CE due to the EUV pulse only as the near-IR pulse intensity in our experimental setup is kept well below the threshold for intense field CE. At the long positive time delays, both three and two-body channels are enhanced. Nevertheless, the higher increase in the three-body yields results in a $\sim 4.7\%$ enhancement of the three: two-body ratio. In contrast, the NN-O versus the N-NO bond cleavage ratio exhibits primarily a

transient effect, reaching a maximal enhancement of $\sim 2.4\%$, slightly (~ 40 fs) before the peak of the transient yield increase. This transient enhancement of NN-O cleavage is rapidly quenched, reaching negative $\sim -0.3\%$ value at long time delays.

As the yield of metastable N_2O^{2+} is below $\sim 0.1\%$ of the total CE yield, the experimental uncertainty limit, we interpret the total two- and three-body CE yield increase as due to photo-

transition can account for the mild suppression observed for the NN-O : N-NO ratio at long time delays.

At transient times, the near-IR pulse leads to enhancement of the NN-O:N-NO bond cleavage ratio. This enhancement cannot be attributed only to photo-ionization of a weakly bound Rydberg electron and is tentatively assigned to excitation of the dication. Because NN-O cleavage is less likely on the metastable $^3\Pi$ state, we consider two possible excitation schemes near the FC geometry to the $^1\Pi$ state that are expected to enhance the NN-O cleavage (see blue and green arrows in figure 1).²⁹ Both the $^1\Sigma^+ + h\nu \rightarrow ^1\Pi$ and the $^1\Delta + 2h\nu \rightarrow ^1\Pi$ excitations dissociate the NN-O bond to form a strongly bound $N_2^+(^2\Sigma_u^+)$, while the path towards N-NO bond dissociation is blocked by the high potential barrier. Furthermore, these transitions suppress the N-NO cleavage on the low lying singlet states $^1\Pi$ state. The very same excitations of singlet dication states can occur in the presence of a weakly bound Rydberg electron, which can be ejected by the excitation of its dication core or by a sequential photoionization within the near-IR pulse. Thus, NN-O cleavage can be enhanced near the FC region. However, the time-window for NN-O enhancement is limited as the wavepacket, initiated by the HHG pulse at time zero on one of the singlet $^1\Delta$ or $^1\Sigma$ states, can be expected to time-evolve away from the FC geometry towards elongation of the N-NO bond and prevent photoexcitation to the $^1\Pi$ state. In contrast, Rydberg state photoionization can be expected to be less sensitive to the time evolving dication core, thus accounting for the broad $\sigma \sim 85$ fs transient yield, extending to longer times and peaking ~ 40 fs after the peak enhancement of the NN-O : N-NO ratio.

figures 3a and 3b show the respective KER distributions of the $N^+ + NO^+$ and $N_2^+ + O^+$ CE channels, induced by the EUV pulse alone. The KER peak of the N-NO bond cleavage is centered around 6.4eV, ~ 0.7 eV higher than the KER peak measured for breaking the NN-O bond, in agreement with previous photoionization studies.²⁸ Energetically, the $N_2^+ + O^+$ ground state lies ~ 2.1 eV above the ground state of $N^+ + NO^+$.²⁶ Thus, the lower KER difference implies internal excitation also in the NO^+ product. Furthermore, the KER spectrum of the $N_2^+ + O^+$ channel is broader, with long tails on both high and low KER sides. The high KER tail can be attributed to contributions from higher lying excited states such as the $^1\Pi$ state, while the low KER tail can be explained by energy dissipation into the vibrational excitation of the N_2^+ product. We therefore conclude that both molecular CE products are expected to have significant vibrational excitation.

Figure 3: KER distributions for the (a) $N^+ + NO^+$ and (b) $N_2^+ + O^+$. (c₁-c₈) and (d₁-d₈) show the respective difference KER spectra for the two CE channels as a function of the near-IR pulse delay. Dotted lines indicate the time evolving KER peaks.

ionization of Rydberg ion states by absorption of 1.54eV photons from the near-IR probe pulse. As the ultrafast dissociation dynamics of Rydberg ion states are dominated by the potential of their dication core, the branching ratio between the competing two-body bond cleavage mechanisms returns almost to its unperturbed value at long time delays. Nevertheless, the enhancement of the three : two-body ratio can be attributed to photodissociation of vibrationally excited CE products. For example, as shown by the black arrow in figure 1, a vibrationally excited $N_2^+ X^2\Sigma_g^+$ product of NN-O bond cleavage on the dication ground state can be photodissociated by an allowed transition to the continuum of the $^2\Pi_u$ state of N_2^+ . The low barrier along the NN-O elongation route can be expected to enhance energy dissipation into the ro-vibrational degrees of freedom of the molecular N_2^+ product, making it susceptible to near-IR photodissociation at long time delays. Thus, the presence of a favourable N_2^+ photodissociation

Figures 3c and 3d show the difference in the KER spectrum (relative to EUV only) at long negative time delays, at which the near-IR probe arrives before the EUV pulse. Similar to the branching ratios, the KER spectrum is not affected by a preceding near-IR pulse. As shown in figures 3c₁-c₈ and 3d₁-d₈, for both two-body breakup channels, the increased yield exhibits KER difference spectra that are similar to the KER spectrum of single-photon CE with the EUV pulse alone. Nevertheless, with increasing pump-probe delays up to ~ 700 fs, the peaks of both KER difference spectra appear to gradually shift towards lower KER upto ~ 0.9 eV. Where at longer time scales (measured up to 1.5 ps) the KER peak shifts remain the same.

Because at short internuclear distances, Rydberg ion potentials mimic the potentials of their dication core, the added CE yield due to photoionization of the Rydberg electron exhibits an almost identical KER spectrum as the dissociating dication. However, once the internuclear separation exceeds the Rydberg radius, the potential gap between the Rydberg ion state and its dication core will result in a weaker repulsion and a shift towards lower KER. As shown schematically in Figure 1, the gap reaches its asymptotic maximal value once the long-range Coulomb repulsion decays at distances exceeding 100 a.u. allowing experimental sensitivity to the post dissociation interaction at long distances.

Assuming purely Coulombic $1/(4\pi\epsilon_0 R)$ repulsive potential and neglecting ion – induced dipole interaction, the asymptotic KER shift allows to evaluate the critical distance, beyond which the Rydberg electron is localized on one of the fragments. Thus, at a time delay of few hundred fs the dissociating fragments reach $R_{loc} \sim 16 \text{ \AA}$ (~ 30 a.u.), at which the Coulombic potential of the dissociating dication equals 0.9eV that are screened for the Rydberg ion state.

Taking a closer look at the difference KER spectra near zero time delays, we note a small shift of the KER peak towards

Figure 4: KER distributions of the three-body dissociation of $N_2O_2^+$. Where full dots and open circles represent the $N^+ + N + O^+$ and $N^+ + N^+ + O$ channels respectively.

higher KER, which can be attributed to the one- and two-photon photoexcitation of the dication discussed earlier. In the near threshold study of Zhou et al³⁴, a similar transient KER increase was observed for the NN-O channel and was attributed to the strong field control of the dissociation dynamics on non-Rydberg ion states.³⁴ Furthermore, the high KER tail of the NN-O cleavage channel appears to be suppressed in the difference KER spectra. If indeed the high KER tail originates from the high excited states of the dication, the corresponding Rydberg ion states contribution to the pump-probe signal can be suppressed by competition with a rapid autoionization. Alternatively, the additional excitation by the probe photon could very well result

Figure 5: Dalitz plot representation of three body dissociation of $N_2O_2^+$ into: (a) $N + N^+ + O^+$, (b) $N^+ + N^+ + O$. (c) Shows the mass-weighted Dalitz plot mapping of the three-body momentum triangle. Where the oxygen and nitrogen momenta are marked by the full red and empty blue circles. (d) Simulated Dalitz plot features, corresponding to a sequential CE, followed by an uncorrelated dissociation of the molecular cation.

in dissociation of the molecular product and contribute to the observed enhancement of the three-body dissociation channels.

Three-body fragmentation of the $N_2O_2^+$ dication requires breaking of both the N-N and the N-O bonds. The two bonds can either break simultaneously in a concerted fashion or sequentially. It is important to note that if the NN-O bond dissociates first, sequential dissociation can only lead to the $N + N^+ + O^+$ channel, first reported by Price et al.²⁶ In contrast, initial dissociation of the N-NO bond can produce both the $N + N^+ + O^+$ and the $N^+ + N^+ + O$ product channels. Single photon Coulomb explosion with our EUV pulse results in $\sim 13\%$ three-body dissociation, where the neutral N channel is ~ 2 times more abundant than the neutral O. The full and open circle markers in figure 4 shows the KER spectra of both $N + N^+ + O^+$ and $N^+ + N^+ + O$ channels, respectively. The neutral N channel exhibits a longer tail towards high KER, nevertheless, both spectra peak at ~ 8 eV. The higher KER compared to the two-body breakup is in agreement with the assignment, made by Price et al, of three-body dissociation to higher excited states above ~ 41 eV.²⁶ The measured time resolved difference KER spectra (not shown) exhibit the same spectral shapes as the EUV only spectra shown in Figure 4, where possible small KER shifts as a function of near-IR probe time are below the experimental error due to the limited statistics and KER resolution for the three-body channels. Nevertheless, three-body fragment imaging allows providing dynamical information, beyond the total KER and branching ratios, about the way energy is partitioned between the three atomic fragments.

Three-body momenta correlations in the dissociation plane are best represented in the Dalitz plot representation.^{39–42} Figures 5a and 5b compare the correlations of the neutral N and neutral O channels respectively. The Dalitz plot coordinates are mass-weighted,⁴⁰ such that an uncorrelated three-body breakup obeying momentum conservation exhibits a uniform distribution confined within unit circle.⁴⁰ For convenience, figure 5c shows how different three-body momenta triangles are mapped onto the mass-weighted Dalitz plot representation. Both channels show a tendency towards co-linear geometries, which are mapped to the circumference of the unit circle. The ϵ_O , ϵ_{N1} , and ϵ_{N2} axes of each fragment (kinetic energy divided by the maximal energy allowed by momentum conservation) are indicated on the Dalitz plots. Comparing the oxygens' kinetic energy fraction, which corresponds to the vertical Dalitz plot axis, neutral oxygen products carry less energy than charged oxygen atoms ejected in three-body dissociation. Nevertheless, neutral products are observed to carry a non-negligible fraction of the available KER in CE events. The Dalitz plot of the neutral O channel, shown in figure 5b, is symmetrised because both N^+ cations ejected from the central and edge positions in N_2O are indistinguishable in our experiment. In contrast, neutral N is easily distinguished from the N^+ cation, clearly showing that the oxygen ion is preferably ejected in the same direction as the neutral N atom. Thus, the two times higher yield of the neutral nitrogen is non-trivial and we can tentatively assign the N^+ cation and neutral N to the edge and central N atoms of the parent N_2O respectively.

In a purely sequential $ABC \rightarrow AB + C \rightarrow A+B+C$ mechanism, in which the transient AB can complete a rotation before a sequential fragmentation step, the energy carried by fragment C does not depend on the energy partitioning between fragments A and B. In the Dalitz plot, such an uncorrelated sequential mechanism would exhibit a stripe structure, perpendicular to the kinetic energy axis of fragment C. Figure 5d shows such schematic Dalitz plot stripe features, expected in the case of the different possible sequential mechanisms of CE followed by an uncorrelated lower KER dissociation of the molecular fragment. Comparing the measured Dalitz plots in figures 4a,b with the schematic features in figure 4d, we can conclude that N-NO and NN-O bond cleavages are correlated and preserve the linear geometry of the parent N_2O .

Conclusions

We have explored N_2O^{2+} Coulomb explosion dynamics, initiated by single-photon double ionization with an ultrafast HHG pulse and probed by time delayed near-IR pulse. Time resolved branching ratios, KER and three-body momentum correlations spectra illustrate the competition between the different breakup processes. While at long time delays, NN-O vs. N-NO bond cleavage ratios are affected predominantly by the preferential dissociation of vibrationally excited N_2^+ products, transient enhancement of NN-O breakup is assigned to excitations of the dication core from the two low lying singlet

states to the $^1\Pi$ potential. The transient NN-O:N-NO enhancement occurs on the 85 fs time scale, comparable with the ultrafast transient reported in strong-field control experiments.³⁴ Interestingly, these times are significantly short compared with the ~ 380 fs time scales inferred by Ueyama *et al* from the product angular decoherence in the three-body CE of N_2O^{3+} .³¹ Furthermore, our Dalitz plot analysis of the measured three-body momentum correlations for both the N^++N^++O and the N^++N+O^+ channels indicate that the linear geometry of the parent neutral N_2O is conserved in a correlated Coulombic explosion, in which either the Oxygen or the central Nitrogen are ejected in a neutral atom state. In contrast, strong field CE three-body breakup of N_2O^{3+} were reported to exhibit significant structural deformation before the CE.³¹

Finally, on the time scale of several hundreds of fs, we do observe KER shifts of up to 0.9eV. These longer time scale dynamics are attributed to the potential gap between Rydberg ion states and their dication core, developing due to screening of the long-range Coulomb repulsion. The effect of the potential gap reflects the post dissociation interaction at long distances occurring at correspondingly long time-scales. Thus, it is valuable for interpreting KER shifts in time resolved and control studies in N_2O ,³⁴ as well as in other complex systems exhibiting Rydberg ion dynamics.^{35,36} Further theoretical ab-initio molecular dynamics simulations are needed to fully understand the competing two- and three-body mechanisms described here for the N_2O dication system.

Experimental methodology

The single photon Coulomb explosion imaging setup has been described earlier.^{43,44} Briefly, HHG of broad bandwidth ultrafast EUV pulses is achieved by focusing ~ 2 mJ of <35 fs, 803nm laser pulses at a 1kHz repetition rate in a semi-infinite neon gas cell.^{45,46} The resulting EUV pulses are spatially filtered from the higher divergence near-IR.⁴⁷ Additional 1.5 mJ of the Solstice⁴⁸ laser output are time delayed, mildly focused to ~ 400 μ m and merged with the HHG pulse at a small ~ 1 degree angle at the center of a home built 3D coincidence imaging spectrometer, where both beams cross a skimmed effusive beam of a N_2O sample. Near-IR time delays are scanned in 20 fs time steps and binned in time bins to minimize statistical errors. The cationic products are accelerated and their 3D momenta are imaged in coincidence on a time and position sensitive detector^{35,43} where their masses are uniquely determined from their time of flight. True CE events are disentangled from an overwhelming dissociative ionization background based on the total momentum conservation of two coincident hits on the detector. Any residual contribution from random coincidences is subtracted based on the measured single hit probabilities.

For each three-body dissociation event, the neutral fragment momentum vector and KER are evaluated from the

center of mass (CM) recoil of the detected pair of atomic cations. Due to velocity map imaging,⁴⁹ the CM recoil resolution in the 2D detector plane is superior to the recoil along the time-of-flight axis. Therefore, 3-body momentum correlations are obtained from the projected momenta in the detector plane using the weighted Dalitz plot method.^{39,41,42} Dalitz plot coordinates, originally developed for three equal mass⁴², are mass scaled according to:⁴⁰

$$\eta_1 = \frac{15}{2\sqrt{44}} \times (\epsilon_{N1} - \epsilon_{N2})$$

$$\eta_2 = 2(\epsilon_O - 1)$$

Where ϵ_O , ϵ_{N1} , and ϵ_{N2} are the respective kinetic energy fractions carried away by the Oxygen and Nitrogen fragments, normalized by their maximal kinetic energy fraction allowed by energy and momentum conservation.

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge European Research Council through grant number #306783 and ISF grant #1369/17 as well as equipment from the Wolfson foundation.

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